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An Evaluation of Agricultural Land Consolidation in Türkiye in Terms of the Restriction of Property Rights

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Abstract

The right to property, defined as the right granting individuals the broadest authority over a thing, is protected under both national and international legal frameworks. This protection arises from the fact that the right may be subject to interference by other individuals or even by the state. One such interference is the state's practice of agricultural land consolidation. Since the consolidation process directly affects the right to property, any such process must observe the limitations imposed on this right. In this context, actions relating to consolidation must be carried out by law and for the purpose of public interest. This study first examines the general issue of restrictions on the right to property. It then explains the types of land consolidation practices and, finally, analyzes the implementation stages of the consolidation process individually, within the framework of judicial decisions.

Keywords: Property Right, Agricultural Land, Land Consolidation, Restriction of Ownership.

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1. Introduction

Since the transition of humankind to a settled life, land has held vital importance for all people. This is because land and agricultural activities carried out on it play an indispensable role in sustaining human life. Accordingly, states have continuously strived both to expand their territorial holdings and to enhance agricultural activities on their lands. However, actions taken by states within the scope of such efforts must not unlawfully interfere with the property rights of private individuals. This is a requirement under both national and international legal norms.

In this context, one practice implemented by states to promote agricultural activity on farmland is land consolidation. Land consolidation refers to the process of reorganizing farmlands that have become too small or irregular in shape to allow for efficient agricultural use. Since this process is carried out by the administrative authority, i.e., the legal entity of the state, it directly affects the property rights of private law people.

2. Methods

From a methodological perspective, it is necessary to identify the rules to be followed in land consolidation carried out by the administration and to explain the restrictions on property rights. In order to properly determine these restrictions, judicial decisions in which such restrictions are addressed constitute another method followed in this study.

The basic method employed in this study is the method of analysis and synthesis. The normative method was applied to examine the existing provisions of the relevant legislation and, where necessary, to develop proposals. Finally, the comparative method was used; given that land consolidation involves restrictions on property rights, the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights concerning restrictions on property rights were also assessed with the aim of contributing to this study.

3. Discussion and Results

3.1. In General: The Restriction of the Right to Property

The right to property is the right that grants a person the broadest authority over a thing. Although this right is not explicitly defined in the Turkish Civil Code (TCC), its content is

regulated. The relevant provision is set forth in Article 683/1 of the TCC as follows: “*The owner of a thing has the authority to use, benefit from, and dispose of it as they wish, within the limits of the legal order.*” Accordingly, the owner, by holding the right to property, obtains the authority to use, benefit from, and dispose of the subject matter of the right. (Oğuzman, Seliçi & Oktay-Özdemir, 2022, p. 313; Akipek, Akıntürk & Ateş, 2018, p. 375; Ayan, 2012, p. 3; Eren, 2012, p. 10; Ertaş, Serdar & Gürpınar, 2012, p. 207; Esener & Güven, 2015, p. 171; Hatemi, 2020, p. 65; Nomer & Ergüne, 2023, p. 197; Sirmen, 2021, p. 261; Örucü, 1976, p. 21 ff.; Arıkan & Oktay, 2023, p. 119; Kılınçtürk Topal, 2019, p. 16; Gürgenburan, 2021, p. 5; Eser Kapcak, 2025, p. 19; Bulut, 2006, p. 25; Gemalmaz, 2015, pp. 379–380; Korkmaz, 2010, p. 119; Gemalmaz, 2009, p. 25 ff.; Başpınar, 2009, p. 92; Kalabalık, 2017, p. 574.)

Although the right to property provides the broadest authority to its holder, as with any right, it may be subject to restrictions under certain conditions (Akkuş, 2024, p. 192; Onaran Ertan, 2023, p. 29; Yiğit, 2016, p. 1219; Kılınçtürk Topal, 2019, p. 21; Gürgenburan, 2021, p. 7; Eser Kapcak, 2025, pp. 19–20; Yavuz, 2019, p. 12; Bulut, 2006, p. 25; Şimşek, 2013, p. 30; Korkmaz, 2010, pp. 116–117; Örucü, 1976, pp. 40–41; Gemalmaz, 2009, p. 446; Kalabalık, 2017, pp. 576–577; Şaşı, 2019, p. 263). In Turkish law, the regulation regarding the restriction of the right to property is found in Article 35, paragraph 2 of the 1982 Constitution of the Republic of Turkey, titled “Right to Property.” The provision is as follows: “*These rights may be restricted only by law and for public interest.*” As clearly seen, the right to property may only be restricted by law and for the purpose of public interest. Constitutional Court decisions also affirm that the right to property does not grant unlimited powers to its holder and may be restricted where public interest so requires (Constitutional Court Decision dated 19.12.2013, App. No. 2013/817, Mehmet Akdoğan and Others; Constitutional Court Decision dated 02.02.2017, App. No. 2014/1546, Recep Tarhan and Afife Tarhan, kararlarbilgibankasi.anayasa.gov.tr). It has also been stated in judicial decisions that the right to property may be restricted only by law and solely for the purpose of serving the public interest (Court of Cassation, 1st Civil Chamber. (2007). Decision No. 2007/10635 (File No. 2007/9091), 7 November 2007; Court of Cassation, General Assembly of Civil Chambers. (2012). Decision No. 2012/640 (File No. 2012/415), 28 September 2012; Court of Cassation, 5th Civil Chamber. (2014). Decision No. 2014/23097 (File No. 2014/7923), 2 October 2014)

Another provision concerning the right to property and its restriction is Article 1 of Protocol No. 1 to the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), titled “Protection of Property.” The relevant provision states: “*Every natural or legal person is entitled to the peaceful enjoyment of his possessions. No one shall be deprived of his possessions except in the public interest and subject to the conditions provided for by law and by the general principles of international law.*” From this provision, it is concluded that three conditions must be met simultaneously in order to lawfully restrict the right to property: the restriction must (i) be in the public interest, (ii) be based on conditions prescribed by law, and (iii) be compatible with the general principles of international law (Akkuş, 2024, p. 197; Çaptuğ Dilek, 2024, p. 325; Yiğit, 2016, p. 1220; Kılınçtürk Topal, 2019, p. 27; Gürgenburan, 2021, pp. 30–31; Gemalmaz, 2015, pp. 386–388; Şimşek, 2013, p. 30 ff.; Örucü, 1976, pp. 41–43; Gemalmaz, 2009, p. 447 ff.; Gözler, 2023, p. 342 ff.; Başpınar, 2009, p. 192 ff.; Perdecioğlu, 2020, p. 116

ff.; Kalabalık, 2017, pp. 577–578; Tezcan, Erdem, Sancakdar & Önok, 2019, p. 647 ff.; Şaşı, 2019, p. 278 ff.).

As seen, the right to property is protected under both national and international legal frameworks. These frameworks also foresee that the right to property may be restricted. However, what is essential in any such restriction is that it must be imposed for the purpose of public interest and must be based on a legal regulation. In this regard, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) also evaluates whether there has been an interference with the right to property in light of the aforementioned principles (ECtHR, *Sporrong and Lönnroth v. Sweden*, App. Nos. 7151/75; 7152/75, Judgment dated 23.09.1982; *Perdigão v. Portugal*, App. No. 24768/06, Judgment dated 16.11.2010; *Anželika Šimaitienė v. Lithuania*, App. No. 36093/13, Judgment dated 21.04.2020; *Hakan Ari v. Turkey*, App. No. 13331/07, Judgment dated 11.01.2011, hudoc.echr.coe.int).

3.2. Agricultural Land Consolidation

Land consolidation refers to the process of restructuring and combining agricultural lands that have become unsuitable for agricultural activity due to various reasons—such as fragmentation through inheritance, natural disasters, or shared ownership sales—or those with irregular physical shapes. The regulation concerning agricultural land consolidation is set forth under Article 1(c) of the Law on Agricultural Reform Concerning Land Arrangement in Irrigation Areas, which states: “*The aim is to consolidate fragmented agricultural lands that no longer allow for economic production by expanding them when necessary and within available means, and to prevent the division and reduction of agricultural lands to a size insufficient for the family’s livelihood and for utilizing family labor.*” As can be seen, consolidation of agricultural land is carried out in order to eliminate the problems that hinder the development of agricultural activity. (Eren & Başpınar, 2017, pp. 142–143; Güzel, 2021, p. 4; Yılmaz, 2019, p. 104; Şenol, 2018, p. 23; Güzeliçar, 2024, p. 59; Küsek, 2014, p. 2; Demirtaş & Sarı, 2016, p. 49; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, pp. 75–76; Boyraz, 2008, p. 565.)

There are two types of land consolidation conducted for the purpose of improving agricultural activity: voluntary consolidation and mandatory consolidation (Eren & Başpınar, 2017, pp. 146–147; Şenol, 2018, pp. 87–88; Güzeliçar, 2024, p. 61; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 78).

Voluntary consolidation is the process of land consolidation conducted with the consent of agricultural landowners. However, unanimous consent of all landowners is not required. The legislator accepts the consent of a certain proportion of owners as sufficient (Eren & Başpınar, 2017, p. 147; Şenol, 2018, p. 87; Güzeliçar, 2024, p. 62; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 78). The qualified majority required for consolidation is regulated under Article 755/1 of the Turkish Civil Code as follows: “*If improvements such as correcting water channels, irrigation, draining swamps, road building, afforestation, or land consolidation can only be carried out through the collective efforts of landowners, such works may be conducted only if two-thirds of the landowners, owning more than half of the land in question, agree to*

the project. Other landowners must comply with this decision. The decision is recorded in the declarations section of the land registry.” As can be seen, a qualified majority is required for land consolidation. Two-thirds of the landowners must agree, and these owners must collectively possess at least half of the total land area.

Although Article 755/1 of the TCC includes a provision regarding voluntary consolidation, an additional provision is also found in Article 5/6 of the Regulation on the Implementation of Land Consolidation and On-Farm Development Services. The provision states: “*Voluntary consolidation shall be carried out with the written consent of landowners (or their legal representatives) who own more than half of the land and constitute more than half of the total number of landowners within the project area. This consent must be obtained by the State Hydraulic Works (DSİ) or the project authority prior to the Presidential Decree and must be included in the justification.*” This provision introduces a different majority rule that is inconsistent with the TCC. Since it is regulated by a secondary regulation, this rule is currently in violation of the law. If an action is taken on the basis of this provision, landowners who do not consent to the consolidation may claim the unlawfulness of the procedure. Therefore, the provision on the required majority for voluntary consolidation should be removed from the regulation. If a different majority requirement than that in TCC Article 755/1 is to be adopted, such rule should be incorporated into the primary legislation—namely, the Law on Agricultural Reform Concerning Land Arrangement in Irrigation Areas, which serves as the legal basis for the regulation.

The second type of land consolidation—mandatory consolidation—refers to consolidation carried out by the administrative authority under a statutory mandate, without requiring the consent of agricultural landowners. This procedure, which directly affects the right to property, is implemented by the administration based on the justification of public interest (Eren & Başpınar, 2017, p. 147; Şenol, 2018, p. 88; Güzuluçar, 2024, p. 62; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 78). For this reason, it is essential that the purpose of public interest be clearly demonstrated in mandatory consolidation practices. Otherwise, landowners may allege unlawfulness. In practice, disputes are more commonly observed in cases of mandatory consolidation.

In one ruling by the Council of State (Danıştay), it was stated that although the land consolidation was implemented as a project, the process nevertheless constitutes an administrative act that produces subjective effects on the landowners’ properties. The same judgment emphasized that the authority granted to the administration regarding consolidation directly affects property rights and that any resulting disputes must be resolved within the framework of the right to a fair trial (Council of State, 17th Chamber, Decision No. 2015/9490 E., 2015/3116 K., dated 01.07.2015, www.legalbank.net).

3.2.1. Implementation Stages of Land Consolidation

The land consolidation process in agricultural areas is carried out pursuant to the provisions of the Agricultural Reform Law on Land Arrangement in Irrigation Areas and the Regulation on Land Consolidation and On-Farm Development Services issued based on this

Law (hereinafter referred to as the relevant Regulation). Due to its importance, the implementation stages of the land consolidation process are examined one by one below.

3.2.1.1. Determination of the Consolidation Area

The first stage of the land consolidation process is the determination of the area where the process will be implemented. The implementation area is determined in accordance with Article 5 of the relevant Regulation. The authority responsible for identifying the area of implementation within agricultural lands is the General Directorate of State Hydraulic Works (hereinafter referred to as “DSİ”). DSİ may exercise this authority directly or delegate it to another institution or organization. However, even if such authority is delegated, DSİ remains responsible for the determination of the implementation area. Following the identification of the project area, a preliminary feasibility report is prepared regarding the findings. After this report, the implementation phase of the project begins. (Güzel, 2021, p. 20; Şenol, 2018, pp. 94–95; Güzeluçar, 2024, p. 63; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 78)

3.2.1.2. Land Grading

Once the feasibility report for land consolidation has been prepared, the process proceeds to the grading of the designated lands. Land grading is conducted to determine the value of new lands to be allocated to landowners based on the grades assigned as a result of the land consolidation project. This process is carried out pursuant to Article 11 of the relevant Regulation. The competent body for this grading process is the Land Grading Commission, which is established in accordance with Article 10(2) of the same Regulation. This commission evaluates the lands based on their location, distance from the farm center, and other physical characteristics. Fixed facilities on the agricultural land are not taken into consideration during the grading process. (Güzel, 2021, p. 23; Şenol, 2018, p. 95; Güzeluçar, 2024, p. 64)

Once land grading is completed as described above, the results are announced in accordance with Article 12 of the relevant Regulation. The provision on public announcement is as follows: *“The property list and land grading map showing the equivalency transformation coefficients determined by the Land Grading Commission and their counterparts in unit values of parcels shall be publicly displayed in the local area; at the village headman's office, village assembly hall, village mosque, the local revenue offices, and the municipal notice boards for thirty days, and also on the internet if appropriate. Other local means may also be used for announcement. An official record shall be prepared for the display process.”* Accordingly, the grading map of agricultural lands is posted for thirty days at various public locations. If appropriate, publication may also be made online. After the announcement, a fifteen-day objection period begins following the expiry of the thirty-day announcement. The objection procedure is governed by Articles 12(2) and 12(3) of the relevant Regulation. *“Landowners and other interested parties may submit written objections regarding the land grading within fifteen days following the end of the announcement period to the Land Grading Commission. The Commission shall resolve objections within fifteen days and notify the parties concerned in writing. The amended lists shall be reposted and announced for another thirty days. Interested parties may also submit written objections to DSİ or the project*

authority within fifteen days of the new announcement period. DSI or the project authority shall resolve the objections within thirty days. The decisions of DSI or the project authority are final and shall be communicated in writing. Land grading decisions not objected to within the time period become final.” As clearly indicated, if no objections are raised within the prescribed period, the land grading becomes final. (Güzel, 2021, pp. 24–25; Güzelaçar, 2024, pp. 64–65)

Considering that the land consolidation process is mostly carried out in rural areas and that the ownership right of the landowner is directly affected by this process, it is unacceptable for the announcement concerning grading to be made in accordance with the current provision. This is because notification regarding such a procedure, which directly concerns the right to property, should be carried out not by way of public announcement as regulated within the relevant Regulation, but in accordance with the service of process procedures set forth in the Notification Law (Güzelaçar, 2024, p. 65). This requirement arises from Article 35 of the 1982 Constitution of the Republic of Turkey, titled “*Right to Property*” as well as Article 1 of the Protocol to the European Convention on Human Rights, titled “*Protection of Property*”.

This matter has also been expressed in the same way in a decision of the Council of State. The aforementioned decision of the 17th Chamber of the Council of State, numbered 2015/9490 E., 2015/3116 K., dated 01.07.2015, is as follows: “*...In the case at hand, the land consolidation process carried out is, in essence, closely related to the right to property, which is recognized as a fundamental human right under the European Convention on Human Rights. On the other hand, considering its technical nature, which involves engineering practices, it is necessary that the defendant administration notify and explain the process in its entirety to the claimants, so that the parties concerned may fully understand how the implementation has been carried out. From a combined assessment of the aforementioned legislative provisions, it is understood that land consolidation may be carried out for the purpose of increasing agricultural enterprise efficiency and ensuring optimum agricultural land sizes. The land consolidation process takes place through the determination of the implementation area, the grading of land, the identification of ownership status, and the formation of new parcels by means of parcelling. Within this process, it is observed that the method of notification through public announcement is prescribed for the acts established, and objection periods are granted.*

In the dispute, it was stated that the parceling process was not notified to the addressee, that the block and parcel numbers of the immovable property allocated to the plaintiff had changed, that it was unclear whether this change had been announced, and that there was no information or documentation regarding how the changes were notified. Although it is stated that the defendant administration provided information regarding the new procedure conducted upon the plaintiff's objection, it cannot be clearly established that the plaintiff was fully informed about all aspects of the land consolidation procedure in question. The plaintiff stated that they applied to the defendant administration again upon learning of the new regulation subject to the case, which was made upon their initial request, and it is observed that it cannot be determined whether the land registration was completed.

In this case, since the dispute concerns property rights and land consolidation is a subjective process, the public notification cannot be taken as the starting point for the period for filing a lawsuit. Considering that the process has a technical aspect, the plaintiff was not fully informed of all the details, and the changes were not communicated to the plaintiff. the information provided by the defendant administration was insufficient, and the plaintiffs' right to access information was not fully ensured. The interpretation that the statute of limitations has expired would violate the essence of the right of access to court. Therefore, while the case should have been decided by examining the merits of the matter, the decision to dismiss the case on the grounds of the statute of limitations lacks legal merit.

Again, in a decision rendered by the 2nd Administrative Court of the Gaziantep Regional Administrative Court, an assessment equivalent to the above decision of the Council of State was made. In summary, this decision states that consolidation procedures directly affect the property rights of agricultural landowners and therefore all immovable property owners must be notified through official channels. The Regional Administrative Court overturned the first-instance court's decision that the deadline for filing a lawsuit had expired and ruled that the case should proceed to the merits. The decision is as follows: "In the case in question, the land consolidation process established is closely related to the right to property, which is recognized as a fundamental human right under the European Convention on Human Rights. On the other hand, given that the matter is of a technical nature, including engineering applications, it is necessary for the defendant administration to notify the plaintiff of all elements of the process and explain them in detail to ensure that the parties involved fully understand how the process was carried out."

On the other hand, given the nature of the land consolidation process, although it is implemented in the form of a project in an application area, it is an individual process that has subjective effects on each of the immovable properties owned by individuals. it also directly concerns the right of ownership in terms of granting authorities the power to dispose of the immovable properties owned by individuals, and it is clear that legal disputes must be resolved within the framework of the right to a fair trial. Another judgement relevant to this issue reads as follows: *"In the dispute, it is seen that the consolidation process was not notified to the parties concerned, that it could not be clearly established that the plaintiff was aware of all the elements of the land consolidation process that is the subject of the lawsuit, and that the land registry records and farmer registration system documents are not of a nature that would enable the plaintiff to be aware of all the elements of the consolidation process.*

In this case, since the dispute concerns property rights and land consolidation is a subjective process, the ÇKS records cannot be used as the basis for the start of the period for filing a lawsuit. Considering that the process has a technical aspect, the plaintiff was not fully informed of all the details, and the changes were not communicated to the plaintiff. the information provided by the defendant administration was insufficient, and the plaintiff's right to access information was not fully ensured. The interpretation that the statute of limitations has expired would violate the essence of the right of access to court. Therefore, the case should

have been decided by examining the merits of the case, but the decision to dismiss the case on the grounds of the statute of limitations lacks legal merit.

For the reasons stated above, the appellant's appeal is accepted, the decision of the Gaziantep 2nd Administrative Court dated 30/04/2018 and numbered E:2017/2097, K:2018/529 regarding the “dismissal of the case on the grounds of expiration of the time limit” is overturned, and the file is sent back to the Court for a new decision. Since a ruling will be made in the decision to be issued, there is no need to make a separate decision on the costs of the appeal proceedings at this stage. In accordance with the fifth paragraph of Article 45 of the Administrative Litigation Procedure Law No. 2577, the right to appeal is closed. The decision was made by majority vote on February 28, 2019.” (Gaziantep BİM 2nd Administrative Court of Appeal, Case No. 2018/3556, Decision No. 2019/276, dated February 28, 2019, www.legalbank.net)

3.2.1.3. Annotation in the Land Registry

Following the identification of the land consolidation area, an annotation is added to the declarations section of the land registry for the parcels within the designated area in terms of legal transactions. This procedure is regulated under Article 8 of the relevant Regulation as follows: *“In areas declared as land consolidation zones, the annotation stating ‘This land has been included in the land consolidation scope pursuant to Additional Article 9 of Law No. 6200’ shall be requested by the land consolidation authority from the relevant land registry offices to be added to the declarations section of the land registry pages of the parcels notified by the General Directorate of State Hydraulic Works (DSİ) or the project authority. From the date of this annotation until the completion and registration of the consolidation process, any transactions requested by the owner or right holder—excluding unregistered acquisitions—such as transfer, sale, mortgage, promise of sale, subdivision, partition, as well as any registration of real or personal rights or annotations, shall be subject to the approval of DSİ or the project authority.”*

As is clear from the regulation, any legal transaction concerning the agricultural land included in the consolidation process is subject to prior authorization by the DSİ or project authority. This requirement applies to all types of transactions, including sales, mortgages, and parcel divisions (Şenol, 2018, p. 96; Güzuluçar, 2024, p. 64; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 80). In essence, this requirement is a clear indication of how significantly the land consolidation process affects the right to property. Once the annotation is placed in the land registry, the owner of the agricultural land can no longer carry out legal transactions regarding their property without the consent of the relevant authority.

3.2.1.4. Identification of Fixed Structures

In the land consolidation of agricultural lands, structures deemed as fixed installations are, as far as possible, allocated to their original owners. Fixed structures include buildings such as houses, barns, granaries, wells, and treed areas. The parceling plan is prepared with the aim of preserving ownership of such structures (Güzel, 2021, pp. 22–23; Şenol, 2018, p. 97; Güzuluçar, 2024, p. 67). This matter is regulated under Article 16/1(c) of the relevant

Regulation, which states: “Structures that are fixed installations, as well as lands, buildings, and facilities contributing to environmental and aesthetic value, shall be preserved for their former owners to the extent possible in the parceling plan. However, if a landowner has more than one such fixed installation, their request regarding the one structure they prefer shall be taken into account.” As this provision indicates, in cases where a landowner possesses multiple fixed structures, only one of them will be considered during the planning, in accordance with the owner's request.

3.2.1.5. Deduction of Contribution Shares

Following the identification of fixed structures, up to 10% of each agricultural parcel may be deducted as a contribution share in order to provide public services within the land consolidation area. These deductions are intended to serve the common use of landowners and for public facilities. The relevant provision is found in Article 15/1 of the Regulation, which reads: “Contribution shares for common facilities shall be determined before the parceling plan is prepared. Based on the parcel value numbers of the land in the project area, up to 10% may be deducted for common facilities such as roads, irrigation canals, and drainage systems required by the project. If these deductions are insufficient, the additional land requirement shall be met through treasury land, public domain land, or, if necessary, through agreement or expropriation from real or legal persons. No compensation shall be paid for the contribution shares allocated to common facilities, and these areas are not subject to registration. However, facilities within the project area that later require licensing—such as transformer stations, resting or storage pools—shall be registered in the name of the Treasury. Expropriation may be carried out by the project authority for integrated structures located on contribution shares.” This regulation clearly states that no compensation shall be paid for the deducted areas. In practice, the 10% deduction limit is occasionally exceeded. In such cases, treasury land is provided in return. However, disputes often arise due to alleged differences between the value of the deducted land and the value of the land provided in compensation. Following the deduction of contribution shares, block plans are prepared as part of the land consolidation implementation (Güzel, 2021, p. 30; Şenol, 2018, p. 101; Güzeliçar, 2024, p. 69; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 82).

3.2.1.6. Interview (Consultation Phase)

Following the preparation of block plans that incorporate the deduction of contribution shares, the land consolidation process proceeds to the interview phase. In this phase, farmers’ preferences are gathered based on the block plans. During these interviews, farmers are asked to express their preferences regarding which parcels they would like to receive or which parcels they wish to be consolidated.

However, these requests submitted by the farmers are not binding on the implementing authority. Despite the lack of legal obligation, distribution in practice generally aligns with the preferences expressed during the interview phase. Nevertheless, it is often not feasible to fully accommodate all requests. Given the typically broad scope of consolidation projects and the large number of landowners involved, it is unrealistic to satisfy every individual request

entirely. In this regard, the implementing authority carries out the distribution process by accommodating the requests of landowners to the extent possible (Güzel, 2021, pp. 30–31; Şenol, 2018, pp. 100–101; Güzeliçar, 2024, p. 70; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, pp. 82–83).

3.2.1.7. Preparation and Registration of the Parceling Plan

After all the previously described stages of land consolidation are completed, the process advances to the preparation of the parceling plan. The plan for the new parcels created as a result of the project is regulated under Article 16 of the relevant Regulation. The provision is as follows: *“The reorganization of the project area by the project authority shall be carried out or commissioned in accordance with the following:*

a) Taking into account the landowners’ requests, after deducting up to ten percent for contribution shares from parcel value numbers, an area of equal value is to be allocated, preferably as a single parcel, based on the order of preference.

b) If there are rights attached to the land, those parcels shall be subject to parceling in line with the opinions of the beneficiaries.

c) Fixed structures and aesthetically valuable lands, buildings, and facilities shall be allocated, to the extent possible, to their former owners. If an owner has multiple such structures, preference will be given to the parcel surrounding one of them, based on the owner’s request...”

This provision sets out detailed rules regarding the parceling plan within the land consolidation process. Based on this rule, the parceling plans are prepared and published in accordance with Article 17 of the Regulation. These plans are announced via public notices posted in locations such as village halls, village mosques, village headmen’s offices, the offices of the local treasury departments, and municipal notice boards (Güzel, 2021, pp. 31–32; Güzeliçar, 2024, pp. 70–71; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 83).

The method of announcement for parceling plans closely resembles the one used for land classification. However, since land consolidation directly affects property rights, this announcement method is considered unlawful. This view is also confirmed in judicial decisions. As emphasized in the section on land classification, any notification regarding land consolidation that directly affects property rights must be made clearly and in detail, in accordance with the Notification Law, in a manner comprehensible to the landowners. Since relevant court decisions are already cited in the previous section, they are not repeated here. However, another decision by the 17th Chamber of the Council of State (Danıştay) regarding the failure to provide proper notice—and therefore the inability to consider the statute of limitations as having begun—states: *“Although land consolidation may be carried out to improve agricultural productivity and achieve optimal parcel sizes, the process includes several stages such as designating the project area, classifying land, identifying ownership, and creating new parcels via parceling. Although public announcements and objection periods are foreseen in this process, there are no specific rules regarding how decisions taken after objections to the new ownership lists—resulting from parceling—should be communicated.*

Moreover, despite land consolidation being implemented across a project area, it produces individual effects on each property and constitutes an administrative act that directly concerns the right to property. As such, legal disputes must be resolved under the principles of fair trial.

In this case, the parcel decision was not individually notified to the concerned parties. No evidence was presented regarding how the rejection of the objection by the claimant was communicated. The records used as a basis for notification lacked a date, and the claimants stated that they were informed over a single rushed day, contrary to the stated three-day duration. The claimants only became aware of the new parcel allocations after boundary stakes were placed and subsequently requested new title deeds from the cadastre directorate. However, the cadastre office replied that the new title records had not yet been finalized. The present case was filed based on this information. Therefore, given that the dispute concerns the right to property and the subjective nature of land consolidation acts, public announcement cannot be deemed a valid method to initiate the statute of limitations. Since the notification process was inadequate and the plaintiffs' right to access information was not fully ensured, accepting that the limitation period has expired would violate their right to access a court. Thus, a ruling on the merits of the case is required rather than dismissal due to the statute of limitations." (17th Chamber of the Council of State, Decision No. 2015/9249 E., 2015/841 K., dated 24.03.2015 – www.legalbank.net)

Objections regarding the parceling plan must be submitted in accordance with Article 17 of the Regulation and reviewed by the DSİ or project authority. After these objections are resolved, the finalized parceling plans are submitted to the cadastral directorate for approval under Article 18. Upon approval, the plans are then forwarded to the land registry office for registration (Güzel, 2021, pp. 31–32; Güzuluçar, 2024, pp. 73–74; Boztoprak, Demir & Çoruhlu, 2016, p. 84).

4. Conclusion

Technological advancements and evolving needs in agricultural activities on farmland have brought about significant developments and changes. Land consolidation has emerged as a necessity driven by these changes and developments. However, since land consolidation is a procedure carried out by states concerning fragmented or physically irregular agricultural lands, and this procedure directly affects the property rights of landowners, the implementation must not violate property rights. Property rights are protected both under the Constitution and the European Convention on Human Rights. These national and international legislations also regulate how this right can be restricted. Accordingly, property rights may only be limited by law and for the public interest.

Since land consolidation directly concerns property rights, all transactions carried out within this practice must be based on laws enacted for public interest purposes. According to Turkish law, land consolidation is executed pursuant to the Agricultural Reform Law on Land Arrangement in Irrigation Areas and the Regulation on the Implementation of Land Consolidation and On-Farm Development Services, enacted based on this law. According to

the legislation mentioned, there are two types of land consolidation: voluntary and compulsory. The first, voluntary consolidation, is carried out with the consent of agricultural landowners. The legislator deems the consent of a certain majority of owners sufficient. However, while Article 755/1 of the Turkish Civil Code requires the consent of two-thirds of the owners who possess at least half of the lands, Article 5/6 of the Land Consolidation Regulation adopts a different majority principle, accepting the consent of only half of the owner's requesting consolidation. This majority rule in the Regulation conflicts with the Civil Code. Since this majority is regulated by a bylaw, its application is not legally possible. Therefore, the provision on the required majority for voluntary consolidation should be removed from the regulation, and if a different majority principle is to be adopted, it should be regulated in the Agricultural Reform Law itself. As a result, since the restriction relating to the right to property must be made by law, this provision in the regulation should be removed, and the amendment should be made in the relevant statute.

The second type of land consolidation, compulsory consolidation, is carried out by the administration without requiring the consent of the agricultural landowners. Since land consolidation directly affects property rights and compulsory consolidation is conducted without the owners' consent, disputes generally arise more in this type. Therefore, in compulsory consolidations carried out by the administration, the objective of public interest must be lawfully and clearly demonstrated. This is also explicitly expressed in Council of State rulings.

The initial step of land consolidation, which directly affects property rights, is the land survey and determination of the implementation area. After this step is completed, the process moves to land classification and its announcement. Land classification is carried out by a land grading commission established according to the relevant regulation. After classification, the results are announced for thirty days on notice boards at village headman's offices, village halls, mosques, and other related locations. Considering that land consolidation directly affects property rights, this announcement method is inappropriate. Notifications related to classification must be made to the landowners through formal procedures under the Notification Law, containing all necessary details. This is also confirmed in decisions of the Council of State and Regional Administrative Courts. Therefore, statutory regulations must be enacted to ensure that notifications are made in accordance with the provisions of the Notification Law.

Following the determination of the project area, an annotation is made in the declarations section of the land registry pages for the parcels within the area. This annotation prevents any disposal or transaction on the agricultural lands without the permission of the General Directorate of State Hydraulic Works (DSİ) or the project authority. It is likely that fixed facilities such as houses, barns, haylofts, granaries, or wells exist on agricultural lands within the scope of the project. In such cases, these fixed facilities are considered when preparing the parceling plan, and the plan is designed so that these fixed facilities are allocated to their former owners as much as possible.

In land consolidation projects, a participation share deduction of up to 10% may be made from each agricultural parcel for the purpose of providing public services. After this deduction, block plans are created. Following the preparation of block plans, the interview phase begins, where farmers convey their preferences regarding which parcels they wish to receive or combine. The project authority considers these preferences as far as possible when distributing the land. This matter also constitutes a requirement that any restriction relating to the right to property must be carried out based on public interest. For the demands of the farmers, who are the addressees of the land consolidation practice, to be taken into consideration is a necessity in terms of ensuring that the planned implementation serves the public interest.

The final step in the land consolidation process is the preparation and registration of parceling plans. These plans are prepared by the DSİ or project authority and announced according to the relevant regulation. The announcement procedure here resembles the one used in land classification. However, since land consolidation directly affects property rights, this announcement method is also unsuitable. Courts have similarly emphasized this point. Ultimately, every notification concerning land consolidation, which directly affects property rights, must be made clearly and comprehensively in accordance with the Notification Law. Therefore, we believe that amending the relevant regulation would be appropriate. Because this matter constitutes an essential requirement for land consolidation, which inherently entails a restriction on the right to property.

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